

Title: The Century-Old Mystery of Gravity

The premise: Starting from the irrationality of free fall, it inspires the cause of gravity generation and the essence of weight, and stimulates the century-old mystery of the essence of gravity, the Law of Void-Induced Force. Theme: The Century-Old Mystery of Gravity, the essence of gravity is the ultimate law of the Law of Void-Induced Force, also an ironclad law. The Law of Void-Induced Force is divided into two main parts: 1. The explanation of the free fall phenomenon. 2. The cause of Force-Induction generation.

The explanation of the free fall phenomenon is further divided into five key elements, among which 1, 2, and 4 are laws:

1. Universal Gravitation
2. The Force-Induction intensity is the same.
3. The concept of the fictional Force-Induction coefficient and the Anti-Mutual Attraction.
4. All things are weightless.
5. All things are floating in cosmic space.

The cause of Force-Induction generation is the Void Expansion Force and the Particle-Tendon Anti-Void Expansion Force.

From free fall, it can be seen that an iron ball and a feather falling to the Earth's surface belong to 1. 'Universal Gravitation', which was already published earlier by Newton. Falling simultaneously belongs to 2. 'Why is the Force-Induction intensity the same?' This involves the cause of Force-Induction generation. As everyone knows, all things are composed of indivisible fundamental particles. What exactly is Force-Induction? How does it operate and how is it generated? It is composed of (One) Void, (Two) Fundamental Particles, (Three) Softness, (Four) Tendon nature and Toughness. Among them, Softness and Tendon nature are the core reasons for Force-Induction generation.

Softness? That's right, fundamental particles are soft, not hard. Is there anything in the world that can simulate fundamental particles being soft and representing their 'existence'? It is a drop of water. When an irregular drop of water or a fundamental particle is expanded by the void—it's not that the void is inflating and expanding, but rather the water drop and particles are pulled by the void, causing them to expand in all directions, forming a truly round sphere. How soft must a particle be to be expanded by the void? It must be as soft as water. If it's like jelly, soft yet hard inside, it will not be expanded by the void, and thus will not generate Force-Induction.

So why does the void plus soft particles plus tendon nature generate Force-Induction? As mentioned before, when an irregular water drop or fundamental particle is expanded by the void, the void applies an expansion force to the particle. This is an

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action force, the Void Expansion Force. The soft fundamental particles possess tendon nature. Due to the void applying expansion force to the particle, they receive a reaction force to resist the expansion force. The particle receives this reaction force, and because the force cannot dissipate, it generates 'Induction'—this is the Particle-Tendon Anti-Void Expansion Force. This is the source of Force-Induction intensity. All particles generate the same Force-Induction intensity. This undissipated force generates 'Induction', which concentrates towards the center of the particle sphere. This is why Force-Induction concentrates towards the center of the Earth—the Earth's center Force-Induction.

The Force-Induction generated by the reaction force causes the entire spherical particle, because the force cannot dissipate, to generate 'Induction'. There is force first, then induction. Therefore, it should be called 'Universal Force-Induction', not 'Universal Gravitation'. It is because there is an undissipated force that generates induction, not because of mutual attraction that generates force. If particles do not possess tendon nature, they will be pulled and expanded by the void until they inflate and vanish into dust. Particles with tendon nature can be compared to a rubber band stretched open with both hands; the hands are the action force, and after stretching, you get the reaction force from the rubber band. This force concentrates towards the center of the rubber band. Particles without tendon nature can be compared to blowing up a balloon. If this balloon lacks tendon nature, it will be blown up until it bursts. However, nature has no obligation to set that water drops and particles stop after expanding into a sphere, and not keep expanding until they inflate and vanish. Therefore, fundamental particles must be soft and possess tendon nature.

Seeing this, I believe everyone should understand why Force-Induction only has a unidirectional attractive force and no repulsive force. Actually, it is simply action force and reaction force. That is to say, it is a very ordinary, very common force, like throwing a stone, etc... Have you ever seen a stone thrown, and before it hits a wall, it is bounced back midway by a repulsive force?

How to prove that undissipated force generates 'Induction'? Create a reaction force, let the force not dissipate, and observe whether an artificially induced mutual attraction, an artificial Force-Induction, is generated.

The aforementioned identical Force-Induction intensity can be compared to an electric wire cut open, containing ten thin copper wires. Insert them individually into ten sockets; each will receive 110 volts of voltage. Pull them out, bundle them into one, and insert them into a single socket; the voltage obtained is still 110 volts, it will not become 1100 volts. Therefore, decomposition and combination do not change

the form of its voltage. The above analogies are very important and can explain why

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the iron ball and feather fall simultaneously despite different weights. This will be used later.

How to prove that the Force-Induction intensity is the same? Send the feather to the Moon, leave the iron ball on Earth in a vacuum environment. Raise the feather away from the lunar surface and the iron ball away from the Earth's surface to the same height. Observe their falling speed and time difference upon reaching the lunar surface and Earth's surface, to prove whether Newton's 'the greater the mass, the stronger the gravitational force' is correct, or whether the Force-Induction intensity is the same. Because the mass of the iron ball and Earth is greater than the mass of the feather and the Moon (mass refers to volume, not weight), if Newton is correct, then the iron ball's falling time would be shorter and its speed faster. If both falling times and speeds are the same, then Newton is wrong ("the gravitational force of an object is proportional to its mass"), and instead the Force-Induction intensity is the same ("the Force-Induction of an object does not change due to the size of the mass, because the intensity remains unchanged").

Softness and Tendon nature are the core reasons for Force-Induction generation. Then, the concept of the Force-Induction coefficient is the core of the explanation for the free fall phenomenon, and also the core within the core of the entire Law of Void-Induced Force. Without this concept, the entire law cannot be established. The concept of the fictional Force-Induction coefficient is actually the Anti-Mutual Attraction. If I directly use Anti-Mutual Attraction to explain, everyone would be unable to understand, and I wouldn't know how to write it either. Although my mind is clear, I cannot convert it into text. Calling it fictional isn't quite right either; it was what came to my mind when I was young, pondering why the heavier iron ball and the feather fall simultaneously! What about the weight? Where did it go? It made me understand that all things are weightless. The first thing that floated into my mind was the Force-Induction coefficient, which later led to the entire framework of the Law of Void-Induced Force.

Why are all things weightless? Because intensity and weight cannot be confused. Intensity is one part of the cause of Force-Induction generation in the Law of Void-Induced Force, while weight is a human sensation; they cannot be mentioned in the same breath. That is to say, for the iron ball and feather during the falling process until they land simultaneously, (intensity) and (weight) must be separated or decomposed into two parts for consideration.

Part (One): Falling simultaneously belongs to (intensity) falling; until landing on the Earth's surface, the hand must not touch the iron ball and feather, and the thought of

the word 'weight' must not exist in the mind. Remember, this part discusses only intensity and must not involve weight. The previous analogy: decomposing and

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combining the electric wire does not change the form of its voltage. Similarly, the iron ball and feather are also composed of fundamental particles. Because the Force-Induction intensity generated by each particle in the void is the same, regardless of decomposing or combining the iron ball and feather, it does not change their Force-Induction intensity form. That is why they fall simultaneously.

The natural laws of the universe only set that two particles generate mutual attraction and stick together. They do not set that two particles generate Anti-Mutual Attraction to resist the mutual attraction between particles. That is to say, if a 20-kilogram stone lands on or sticks to the Earth's surface, this is the power of mutual attraction granted to them by natural law. Natural law does not set or grant you humans the ability to lift this stone with your hand, causing the stone and the Earth's surface to form an Anti-Mutual Attraction to resist the mutual attraction between the stone and the Earth's surface. Therefore, stones on the Moon and Mars only have mutual attraction and do not have Anti-Mutual Attraction. Only on Earth, this planet, with our sensory perception, do we lift the stone and produce the illusion of weight. This part means that during the falling process, only Force-Induction intensity can be considered; weight cannot be mixed in, otherwise the contradiction arises that the iron ball is heavier than the feather yet they fall simultaneously.

Part (Two): Human factor (weight). Lifting the iron ball and feather upwards by hand violates natural law. This belongs to the Law of Void-Induced Force, Part 1, points 3' and 4'. Assume the iron ball is composed of ten thousand fundamental particles, and the feather is composed of one hundred particles, placed on the ground. Take ten particles each from the iron ball and the feather and lift them upwards. The Anti-Mutual Attraction generated by both is the same, so you would feel they are the same weight. Then, increase the iron ball particles to ten thousand and the feather particles to one hundred; you will feel that the Anti-Mutual Attraction of the iron ball particles is greater than that of the feather particles, and you will feel it's strenuous and heavy.

Otherwise, let me use the Force-Induction coefficient to replace Anti-Mutual Attraction. Assume each particle of the iron ball and feather has a rubber band tied to the ground to simulate the action of Force-Induction. When lifting upwards, the quantity of ten thousand rubber bands for the iron ball compared to one hundred for the feather would feel very strenuous and heavy. This is not weight at all; it is the hand resisting the anti-pulling force of ten thousand rubber bands. This was the first thing that came to my mind when I understood that all things are weightless—the

Force-Induction coefficient.

Give another example: divide a table into left and right sides. Tie one hundred rubber bands to the left side and only one rubber band to the right side. Set the strength of

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each rubber band to one pound of pulling force. Use left and right hands to simultaneously lift the one hundred and the one upwards to the same height. The left hand will withstand one hundred pounds of anti-pulling force, the right hand only one pound. Upon release, because the intensity is the same, they will snap back to the table surface simultaneously. Therefore, the greater the number of rubber bands, or the increase/decrease in the number of iron ball/feather particles, will make you feel a greater anti-pulling force and Anti-Mutual Attraction, and thus feel that the iron ball is heavier than the feather. This is false weight, a false weight created by human factors.

If one insists on calling it weight, then the source of the essence of weight is the object's Anti-Mutual Attraction with the Earth's surface, not from the Force-Induction intensity. Humans, with their sensory perception, created the word 'weight' to express this strenuous phenomenon and explain it. Since Aristotle proposed that heavy objects fall to the Earth's surface faster than light ones, the concept of weight has been passed down for over two thousand years and implanted in people's minds. Until Galileo's Leaning Tower of Pisa experiment with two iron balls broke this myth, it also created a contradiction in the free fall phenomenon. There are several puzzles in physics. One, why does mass generate Force-Induction, and how is it generated? Two, why do objects have weight; what is the essence of weight? If the natural laws of the universe truly included weight, then theoretical physics would not only have to find out why objects generate weight, but also find the essence of all phenomena that can create the feeling of strenuousness as weight. Then, the essence of weight could never be fully found. Objects have Anti-Mutual Attraction, rubber bands have anti-pulling force, springs have anti-elastic force—as long as these three generate a phenomenon that makes you feel strenuous, can it be defined as weight? Is that it?

Summary:

(一) Both the iron ball and feather are composed of particles. Subject to the same conditions for Force-Induction generation, they produce the same Force-Induction intensity. Decomposition or combination does not change their intensity form, hence they fall simultaneously.

(二) When the hand's touch sensation contacts the iron ball or feather particles and lifts them upwards, it will, with the increase or decrease in the number of particles, produce a severe feeling of strenuousness or a slight feeling of strenuousness. This is

not weight at all; it is a false weight created by human factors. Simply put, the increase or decrease in the number of fundamental particles determines the magnitude of the Anti-Mutual Attraction between the two objects (the intensity remains unchanged), and the increase or decrease in the number of fundamental

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particles determines the size of the Force-Induction range of an object (the intensity remains unchanged). To counteract the magnitude of the Anti-Mutual Attraction, there is only one way: the applied force must be greater than that force. For example, you can pull one rubber band, but an ant cannot. You cannot pull one hundred rubber bands, but an excavator can. You cannot pull one thousand rubber bands, but a rocket can.

Since all things are weightless, it belongs to the Law of Void-Induced Force, Part 1, point 5'. In ancient times, the Flat Earth theory: why didn't the physicists of that time reference the Moon being round to understand that the Earth is also round? Because they were blinded by societal cognition. Nowadays, why don't we reference the Moon floating to understand that all things are also floating? Because we are blinded by the cognition of weight. The opposite of Flat Earth is the Round Earth; the opposite of the Sun revolving around the Earth is the Heliocentric theory and the Round Earth theory. At that time, they were considered heresy and delusion; the former became banned books, the latter was burned at the stake. Hundreds of years later, they became prophets of truth. Today, I propose the opposite of weight is weightlessness. It may not be accepted by the present era, and hopefully won't lead to being burned at the stake, but in a few hundred years, it will become truth. Flat Earth to Round Earth, Geocentric to Heliocentric, having weight to having no weight—all are breakthroughs in the history of physics.

Since they are floating, why are objects on Earth, the rovers on Mars, and the Apollo lunar module on the Moon firmly pinned to the planet's surface and cannot float in the space above the planet's surface? It is because this Force-Induction generates mutual attraction. If this Force-Induction could be removed, the particles would float above the ground. Objects are composed of particles, likewise. Because the attractive force between the two parties is broken on one side, the necessary condition for attraction between them cannot be met. This is the anti-gravity that scientists have been searching for. If all things fundamentally have no weight, then where does gravity come from? Let alone anti-gravity.

So, the eyes see a straight line and take the Earth as flat. Seeing the sun rise in the east and set in the west, one concludes the sun revolves around the Earth. Seeing the watermelon rind is green, one thinks the watermelon flesh is also green. When lifting something feels strenuous, one takes it as weight. One is visual, one is sensory—they

actually blind us to the cognition of the universe's natural laws, thus causing us to lose the pursuit of the truth and meaning of natural laws. If there is Force-Induction, there cannot be weight; if there is weight, there cannot be Force-Induction. The simultaneous existence of both creates a contradiction between visual and tactile senses. Force-Induction does not produce weight, but Anti-Mutual Attraction

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produces false weight.

Physics is the principle of matter, which must be established on the occurrence of natural phenomena, such as lightning and birds flying, leading to scientific progress that benefits humanity. The contradiction in the free fall phenomenon is also a natural phenomenon, from which the mystery of gravity can be unraveled. However, in general relativity, gravity bends spacetime without any phenomenon occurring. Birds flying and lightning are visually natural and can be seen, whereas spacetime curvature cannot be seen. This indicates that the creator of the universe created the laws of natural phenomena but did not create the phenomenon of spacetime curvature. On the contrary, Einstein himself played the role of creator, inventing this natural physical phenomenon. We can only unravel the mysteries of the universe's creator, but we cannot play the role of creator to invent natural laws and phenomena; otherwise, more mysteries will arise. Author, Tsai Zong-He,